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Human-snake conflict in an urban environment in southwestern Amazonia: A case study on motivation and interaction with *Eunectes murinus* in Rondônia

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Urban expansion and habitat reduction have caused conflicts between humans and wild animals throughout Brazil (Mascarenhas-Junior et al. 2021; Ruiz-Tagle et al. 2021) and these have intensified in the last 20 years (Marchini & Crawshaw Jr. 2015). In rural environments, conflicts with snakes are mainly preventive because snakes represent a potential risk to domestic animals and humans (Alves et al. 2012; Miranda et al. 2016; Lima et al. 2020). The motivations related to snake-killing in urban

environments may be similar to those in rural environments. Nevertheless, there is a clear need to understand the existing interactions and motivations related to such conflicts.

Snakes are historically portrayed as untrustworthy animals, mainly due to myths and legends (Lima-Santos et al. 2020), which contribute to their systematic killing (Fernandes-Ferreira et al. 2012), including the non-venomous constricting anacondas. The green an-

anaconda (*Eunectes murinus*) occupies aquatic habitats and feeds on a wide variety of animals, including fish, amphibians, chelonians, lizards, snakes, alligators, birds, and mammals such as agoutis, pacas, capybaras, peccaries, tapirs, deer, monkeys, and even domestic species (Strimple 1993; Strüssmann 1997; Martins & Oliveira 1998; Bernarde & Abe 2010; Rivas et al. 2016; Lima et al. 2020; Thomas & Allain 2021).

Although some motivations for killing snakes are related to protection of domestic animals, motivations in urban environments need to be explored, especially when another wild species interacts with the snake. This study reports a conflict between humans and a green anaconda motivated by predation on a bird (*Ramphocelus carbo*).

At 4:56 pm on February 19, 2021, in the municipality of Porto Velho, Rondônia State, Brazil, southwestern Brazilian Amazonia, residents reported the presence of a newborn *Eunectes murinus* on a private property in the city center. The property is within an urban forest fragment crossed by a small river named Santa Barbará (8.768° S, 63.898° W; WGS-84; 87 m above sea level), 1.22 km from the Madeira River (Fig. 1). The properties within the forest fragment do not have any division system, and inhabitants plant fruit trees in the forest. The fruit is used as food for

both residents and birds. The residents contacted the senior author for the removal of an *E. murinus* from the top of a banana tree (*Musa* sp.), where it was said to be preying on silver-beaked tanagers (*Ramphocelus carbo*). According to the residents, silver-beaked tanagers are common in the locality and are always seen feeding on fruit trees; the birds' presence is appreciated and accepted as positive. Residents killed the snake for fear and because it was preying on birds.

The *Eunectes murinus* specimen was collected (Fig. 2A–B), and the stomach contents were dissected and analyzed, revealing that it had consumed a *Ramphocelus carbo* (Fig. 2D). The snake was deposited in the Coleção Herpetológica da Universidade Federal de Rondônia (UFRO-HEP 003318) and its prey was deposited in the Coleção de Referência da Avifauna do Estado de Rondônia (UFRO-AVE 000288). Both snake and bird were preserved in 70% ethanol. The *E. murinus* (Fig. 2C) was a male, ca. 86 cm total length, and 329 g weight. The *R. carbo* (Fig. 2D) was a male, identified by white spots on its beak (Sick 1997), ca. 11 cm total length, and 46 g weight.

In many regions of Brazil, feeding birds is a part of the human population's daily activity (Crepaldi et al. 2018), demonstrating a very close relationship between humans and birds, as observed

in the study site. Therefore, the predation of birds by snakes can be negatively interpreted by residents, even though it is a natural event, and birds, including *Ramphocelus carbo* (Bagno et al. 2012), are a common component of the diet of *E. murinus*.

Snakes of the genus *Eunectes* suffer from human pressure for illegal breeding, the commercial use of their skin, and their fat for traditional medicine (Alves et al. 2006; Souza et al. 2017; Ramos et al. 2020; Oliveira et al. 2021), besides being considered aggressive (Waldez & Vogt 2009). An essential aspect of the conflict between humans and snakes is the snakes' diet. In the event reported here, residents exhibited a clear preference for the prey (bird) over the predator (snake). This indicates the need to communicate the importance of snakes, especially in urban environments. Educational activities on the behavior and diet of snakes should be directed toward reducing hostile behaviors toward these animals (Moura et al. 2010). This report reinforces the need for environmental education for demystifying snakes and their ecological relationships, especially regarding predation, and the importance of this group to the urban population of Porto Velho.

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REFERENCES

- Alves R.R.N., Filho G.A.P., Lima Y.C.L.C. 2006. Snakes used in ethnomedicine in northeast Brazil. *Environment, Development and Sustainability* 9:455–464.
- Alves R.R.N., Vieira K.S. Santana G.G., Vieira W.L.S., Almeida W.O., Souto W.M.S., ... Pezzuti J.C.B. 2012. A review on human attitudes towards reptiles in Brazil. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 184:6877–6901.
- Bagno M.A., Brandão R. A., Péres-Jr. A. K. 2012 *Eunectes murinus* (Green Anaconda): Diet. *Herpetological Review* 43:493.
- Bernarde P.S., Abe A.S. 2010. Hábitos alimentares de serpentes em Espigão do Oeste, Rondônia, Brasil. *Biota Neotropica* 10:167–173.

- Crepaldi M.T., Pedroso M.F., Ferreira, M.E.M.C. 2018. Columbídeos, zoonoses e possíveis manejos para controle de população: um olhar geográfico. *Periódico Eletrônico Fórum Ambiental da Alta Paulista* 14:155–164.
- Fernandes-Ferreira H., Cruz R.L., Borges-Nojosa D.M., Alves R.R.N. 2012. Crenças associadas a serpentes no estado do Ceará, Nordeste do Brasil. *Sittientibus série Ciências Biológicas* 1:153–163.
- Lima N.S., Napiwoski S.J., Oliveira M.A. 2020. Human-wildlife conflict in the Southwestern Amazon: poaching and its motivations. *Nature Conservation Research* 5:109–114.
- Lima-Santos J., Costa H.C., Molina, F.B. 2020. The curse of being serpentine: perceptions of snakelike animals in São Paulo, Brazil. *Ethnobiology and Conservation* 9:27.
- Marchini S., Crawshaw Jr P.G. 2015. Human-wildlife conflicts in Brazil: a fast-growing issue. *Human Dimensions of Wildlife* 20: 323–328.
- Mascarenhas-Jr P., Maffei F., Muniz F., Freitas-Filho R.F., Costa T.C.G., Campos, Z., Bassetti, L.A.B. 2021. Conflicts between humans and crocodilians in urban areas across Brazil: a new approach to support management and conservation. *Ethnobiology and Conservation* 10:37.
- Martins M., Oliveira M.E. 1998. Natural History of snakes in forests of the Manaus region, central Amazonia, Brazil. *Herpetological Natural History* 6:78–150.
- Miranda E.B., Ribeiro Jr R.P., Strüssmann C. 2016. The ecology of human-anaconda conflict: a study using internet videos. *Tropical Conservation Science* 9:43–77.
- Moura M.R., Costa H.C., São-Pedro V.A., Fernandes V.D., Feio R.N. 2010. O relacionamento entre pessoas e serpentes no leste de Minas Gerais, sudeste do Brasil. *Biota Neotropica* 10:133–141.
- Oliveira, M.A., Doria, C.R.C., Messias, M.R. 2021. A comparison of zotherapy practices between urban and rural hunters in the southwestern Brazilian Amazon. *Etnobiologia* 19:135–153.
- Ramos C.G.S., Santos R.B., Santos R.W.C., Oliveira M.A. 2020. Hunting in a community of waste pickers of recyclable materials in Rondônia, Brazil. *Revista Brasileira de Ciências da Amazônia* 9:4–15.
- Ruiz-Tagle N.M., Nogueira-Filho S.L.G., Knowles, T.G., Nogueira, S.S.C. 2021. Using predator feces as a repellent for free-ranging urban capybaras (*Hydrochoerus hydrochaeris*). *Acta ethologica* 24:205–216.

Rivas J.A., Molina C.R., Corey S.J., Burghardt G.M. 2016. Natural history of neonatal green anacondas (*Eunectes murinus*): a chip off the old block. *Copeia* 104:402–410.

Sick H. 1997. Ornitologia brasileira. Nova Fronteira. Rio de Janeiro.

Souza E., Werneck F.P., Matos L.B., Fraga R. 2017. Zooterapia na Amazônia: gordura anaconda verde (*Eunectes murinus*) como medicamento natural para o tratamento de feridas. *Acta Amazônica* 47:341–348.

Strimple P.D. 1993. The green anaconda *Eunectes murinus* (Linnaeus). *Literatura Serpantium* 13:46–50.

Strüssmann C. 1997. Hábitos alimentares da sucuri-amarela *Eunectes notaeus* Cope, 1862, no Pantanal matogrossense. *Biociências* 5:35–52.

Thomas O., Allain S. 2021. Review of prey taken by anacondas (Squamata, Boidae: *Eunectes*). *Reptiles & Amphibians* 28: 329–334.

Waldez F., Vogt R.C. 2009. Aspectos ecológicos e epidemiológicos de acidentes ofídicos em comunidades ribeirinhas do baixo rio Purus, Amazonas, Brasil. *Acta Amazônica* 39:681–692.

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Figure 1. Site of the interaction between *Eunectes murinus* and humans in Porto Velho municipality, state of Rondônia, Brazil.

Figure 2. Photographic evidence of the consumption of *Ramphocelus carbo* (Pallas, 1764) by *Eunectes murinus* (Linnaeus, 1758). A) Dorsal view of *E. murinus*. B) Ventral view of *E. murinus*. C) Hemipennis of *E. murinus*. D) *R. carbo* found in stomach contents of *E. murinus*.